

iTRACK Policy Handbook

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Glossary

Abbreviation /Acronym	Description
CODs	Common Operational Datasets
DPIA	Data Privacy Impact Assessments
GIS	Geographic information system
GPDR	General Data Protection Regulation
GSM	Global System for Mobile communication
GSMA	GSM Association
HAP	Humanitarian Accountability Partnership
HIC	Humanitarian information center
HPC	Humanitarian programme cycle
IASC	Inter-Agency Standing Committee
ICO	Information Commissioners Office
ICRC	International Committee of the Red Cross
ICT	Information and communication technology
IFRC	International Federation of Red Cross
IM	Information management
IMO	Information Management Officer
IMU	Information management unit
IPC	Information and Privacy Commissioner of Ontario,
IPs	Implementing Partners
ISAC	Information Sharing and Analysis Centers
iTRACK	Integrated system for real-time TRACKing
LIA	Legitimate Interest's Assessment
LSP	Logistics service provider
NGO	Non-governmental organization
OCHA	Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs
OSOCC	On-Site Operations Coordination Centre
PRESCIENT	Privacy and Emerging Fields of Science and Technology
UDHR	The Universal Declaration of Human Rights
UN	United Nations
UN OCHA	United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs
UNDAC	United Nations Disaster Assessment and Coordination
UNDSS	United Nations Department of Safety and Security
UNHCR	United Nations High Commission for Refugees or The UN Refugee Agency
UNISDR	United Nations International Strategy for Disaster Response
WFP	World Food Programme

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1 Methodology

The manual was designed to provide general Information Management guidance to the iTrack core users as a decision-support tool in the control room (Mission leader, security officer, IM officer, and Logistics officer) to deal with dilemmas that arise when using the iTrack system. The guidelines also incorporate the ethical considerations that they should consider and how they can safely use the iTrack system.

Methodologically, D2.7 customizes the [Economic Research Centre's Public Policy Design methodology](#), used to guide the policy formulation process, when there are:

- Different and/or conflicting interests.
- The users of a new innovation do not have a complete picture of the current problem and their required action; and
- There is no established, systematic, efficient, and customized discourse process for the users to adopt in order to reach a consensus.

The methodology comprises of five phases: (1) preliminary and planning phase; (2) situation analysis phase; (3) data collection and analysis phase; (4) policy design phase; and (5) involving social (interest) groups into discourse phase. Each of the phases is described in the subsequent paragraphs.

1. Preliminary and planning phase

A joint WP 2, 3 and 6 team was convened to agree on the scope of the policy design process and identify the key users of the policy instrument. Differences between various competing aims (decision dilemmas) were identified in a Policy Workshop held on the 14th to the 15th of January 2019, in Delft, The Netherlands. During the workshop, ten dilemmas were identified. Five of the decision dilemmas focused on humanitarian information management in conflicts and the other five on the ethical and safe usage of the iTRACK solutions.

2. Situation analysis phase

Based on the scope, the relevant project and policy documents were identified and analyzed. Table 22 (section 11) contains all the relevant iTRACK documents that were analyzed and synthesized. The list of iTRACK deliverables only includes the publicly available documents, though the confidential documents under WP 2, 3 and 6, were analyzed and synthesized into the policy handbook. In addition, the literature reviewed, to guide the policy design process, is contained in section 7, 8 and 12.

3. Data collection and analysis phase

After the January workshop, and the situation analysis, a questionnaire was developed by TUD with the technical input of UIA (Annex D). In the Description of Action (DoA) part of T2.5 on policy design was to use Multi-Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) methods to achieve consistent policy design. The MCDA method was replaced by questionnaires. This change was necessary after consultations with a number of persons who attended previous HNPW meetings. They advised iTRACK use a simpler and less demanding approach because of the nature and design of HNPW meetings. Therefore, the methodology was adjusted to ensure development of an appropriate data collection tool for the planned workshop. Moreover, the questionnaire was designed with multiple decision options and the stakeholders were expected in every dilemma to analyze the options and select the most likely and least likely decisions. Therefore, even

though an MCDA was not used the questionnaire results provided guidance on the most likely decision to address the dilemma, amongst the available decision options.

The policy decision dilemma questionnaire was disseminated widely during 2019 Humanitarian Network Partnership Week (HNPW) in Geneva, Switzerland on the 4th to the 8th of February 2019. This involved placing it on the iTRACK exhibition stand for interested stakeholders to fill it in, sending it by email to the TUD students present in HNPW for onward transmission to people they had talked to and discussion during the iTRACK session on Technology & Innovation in Conflicts.

The iTRACK session was held on Wednesday, 6th February 2019 during the Inter-network day. We distributed the questionnaire that included the ten identified policy dilemmas (Annex D) to the workshop participants. In total, there were thirteen (13) responses. A number opted not to fill in the questionnaire, and recommended that in future, more time should be provided for stakeholders to understand iTRACK and, test the iTRACK solutions, before completing the questionnaire. To address this, WP 8 and 9 leaders invited some of the potential users of iTRACK on 11th April, 2019, for a workshop and a demonstration session, in Delft, The Netherlands.

After the HNPW workshop, all the collected data, both the qualitative and quantitative data (Annex E contains the questionnaire results), were analyzed.

4. Policy design phase

The policy design was undertaken in two stages. First, a description of the current policy situation for select decision dilemmas, and future desired situation. Second, an identification of policy guidelines and checklist of actions, to be able to reach the desired state. We gathered both qualitative and quantitative information during the HNPW workshop (Annex E). We used a mixed method approach to test the effect and acceptance of the policies. The results in HNPW were treated as guidance and formed a small part of the policy handbook. Most of the content from the dilemma was drawn from existing guidelines, that address the same dilemma.

5. Involving social (interest) groups into discourse

At the start of the policy handbook, iTRACK project incorporates a statement welcoming comments on the policy handbook which should be sent to a.m.onencan@tudelft.nl by 30 April 2019. The policy handbook will be available online from 1st April 2019, to provide sufficient time for humanitarian organizations to provide input aimed at improving the current draft.

Further Reading

[Economic Research Centre's Public Policy Design methodology](#)

2 Introduction to iTRACK

IMPORTANT NOTICE

iTRACK project welcome comments on the policy handbook which should be sent to a.m.onencan@tudelft.nl by 30 April 2019.

This policy handbook first introduces iTRACK and after that provides generic guidance to humanitarian information management in conflicts as well as guidelines for ethical and safe usage of the iTRACK solutions.

More guidance:

iTrack website: <https://www.itrack-project.eu/>

You can also take specialized training on this topic using iTRACK training cases.

Training cases website: <https://bit.ly/2IW3eED>

2.1 Whom is this Policy Handbook designed?

This policy handbook is designed for users of the iTRACK system. The main users of iTRACK and their primary responsibilities are outlined in Table 1. The main locations designated for iTRACK use are in the control room, warehouse, convoy (during the humanitarian mission to and from the conflict zone) and in the field.

Table 1. iTRACK users and their primary responsibilities

#	iTRACK user	Primary Responsibilities
1	Mission leader	Mission leader acts as the humanitarian coordinator and is responsible for the whole region at the tactic level. Mission leader holds an overview of the field operations. He receives information on humanitarian aid resources and mission status from the logistics officer, the information of the need requests and field conditions from IMO, and has direct communication with the local government.
2	Information Management Officer (IMO)	IMO is responsible for collecting, processing, analyzing and disseminating all relevant, up to date and reliable information, to facilitate the communication, coordination, and collaboration among all participating parties in the field mission.

#	iTRACK user	Primary Responsibilities
3	Data Coordinator	Data coordinator helps to manage and organize data so that it can be used for assessment and decision-making. Data coordinator also pays attention to standardizing and aligning data processing procedure and format across systems.
4	GIS specialist	GIS specialists collect, present and store data by using GIS to help to understand the field conditions and solve problems.
5	Security officer	Security Officers receive safety, and security-related incidents/notifications receive information about all members and vehicles of a mission and can send reports through the iTRACK mobile application. Their reports are marked with a higher level of reliability than the other users of the iTRACK mobile application.
6	Assessment & monitoring support	This position is responsible for processing and analyzing the data and translating it into meaningful implications for decision-making. They also provide support in monitoring the progress of mission and field situations.
7	IM focal point	IM focal point collects and disseminates information by joining meetings and talking to local communities.
8	Logistic officer	The Logistics Officer creates, monitors, and modifies a logistics plan for the commodities or a route. Moreover, he/she can change intermediate points of a plan or can modify lost, destroyed, or stolen items.
9	Warehouse manager	The Warehouse Manager can modify the status/location of the tracked items either by scanning the QR code that is attached to the items or by manually entering the data into the system.
10	Distribution manager	The Distribution Manager inserts information about the final destination and the distribution of the items to the beneficiaries. He/she also confirms if the delivery of the commodities was completed or not.
11	Transportation manager	The transportation manager is responsible for executing the delivery of assets to the beneficiaries. Usually, local transportation companies are hired to provide drivers and other facilities.
12	Local commercial partners	Local commercial partners can support humanitarian relief efforts by providing different functions, including logistics and transportation, warehouse management/operator, and security. Local transport may be commissioned to transport relief goods. The local warehouse can be used for asset storage. In fragile regions, local security may be hired to protect aid operations and ensure the safety of aid workers.
13	Local NGO partners	iNGOs often establish partnerships with local NGOs to perform field missions. Local NGOs may not be the primary user of iTRACK but may interact with iTRACK internal actors frequently and provide important field information to iNGOs
14	Local government	Local government can provide field conditions and must be informed about the mission progress. Local government does not use the iTRACK system.
15	Local communities	Local communities are the beneficiaries of humanitarian aid and hold critical information about the needs and field conditions.

While using iTRACK, there are anticipated differences among various competing aims of the primary iTRACK users. This policy handbook seeks to identify some of the possible dilemmas that the iTRACK users may face while using the system. For instance, the IMO may request more time to verify rumors received through social media regarding the safety of the mission. However, the logistics officer's aims may conflict with the request for more time, because the commodities being delivered are perishable, or the beneficiaries in the conflict zone are in dire need of food and medication, and there is no time for information verification.

The policy handbook is designed to support the decision-making process when faced with such dilemmas. The handbook also incorporates ethical considerations and guidelines for the safe usage of the iTRACK system, by humanitarian organizations.

2.2 What is iTRACK?

iTrack is a Real-time decentralized system, in which information can be shared in a secure way to enable operational responders to be informed [as opposed to the typical hierarchical setup]. The system was designed to prevent potentially threatening situations, decrease response times and provide useful early warning advisory and policies to decision-makers on staff safety and more effective and efficient response.

2.3 Why use iTRACK?

iTRACK's focuses on improving the protection of humanitarian personnel as well as the commodities of humanitarian, public or private organizations through an integrated tracking solutions to support threat detection, navigation, logistics and coordination in humanitarian disasters. This not only improves protection but also the overall effectiveness and success of humanitarian missions. It has a real-time threat detection mechanism, which enables humanitarian workers to assess the situation, make informed decisions, and communicate and organize their responses accordingly. Moreover, the iTRACK system primarily is developed for the humanitarian community (workers, volunteers, policymakers etc.).

iTRACK is designed to improve the safety and security of humanitarian workers as well as their improved ability to carry out their mission and to serve people in need. The utilization of iTRACK occurs for a variety of different reasons, most notably the safety and security of humanitarian workers, to protect vulnerable populations, to assist with logistics as well as for the organization of humanitarian responses.

2.4 When is iTRACK used?

The iTRACK system focuses on humanitarian operations in conflict zones:

- in real-time; and
- using secure means, e.g., in cases where character identifying information is included and should be protected.

iTRACK is designed for the use in humanitarian operations within conflict zones, which have particular characteristics in common, namely:

1. They are carried out in highly dynamic and volatile environments;
2. Access to various locations, routes, and beneficiary groups is restricted and changes over time;
3. Different humanitarian organizations may be able to access different locations, and may use different types of co-operation partners (CPs) and implementing partners (IPs) for last mile distribution;
4. Due to conflict, many beneficiaries are displaced or on the move;
5. Constant impact of the conflict of infrastructure (transport, communication, energy, health) constrains the use of technology;
6. There is a heightened need for the protection and security of humanitarians, humanitarian assets and commodities, and beneficiaries; and
7. Operations extend beyond the conflict zone to support staging areas in neighboring countries.

At the same time, specific conflict zones also place very stringent constraints not only on the movement of humanitarians and humanitarian cargo but also, on the technologies that can be used. The legal environment and the nature of the conflict affect the feasibility of using various technologies. Differences in mandates and the potential access to different types of humanitarian organizations – apart from differences in their technology readiness - also lead to varieties in use. For example, UN agencies may have access to different parts of a conflict environment than NGOs and have different restrictions on which technologies they can use. Also, the use of various IPs impacts both the possibility to access particular locations and the possibilities for using specific tracking and tracing technologies. To address all these conditions iTRACK system and its components were developed in a modular (independent components that can be used together and separately) and flexible manner.

Further Reading

iTRACK. (2017). D2.4. Humanitarian Logistics Policies & Case Brief [Online]
https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_WP2_D2.4%E2%80%93Humanitarian%20Logistics%20Policies%20&%20Case%20Brief.pdf

3 iTRACK's Contribution to the Current State of Affairs

This section describes the current state of tools and practices and identifies gaps intended to be addressed by the iTRACK system.

4.1 Sensing and tracking

To track staff, humanitarian agencies maintain databases of information used for this purpose. This information includes staff location, staff telephone numbers, staff next of kin, staff physical address and in some cases proof of life questions. Sensing and tracking are currently done using multiple tools. Thus, users have to log into multiple tools, e.g., for the same mission, and sometimes to duplicate required information. This is cumbersome for users. The iTRACK solutions allow different tools to form the back-end of a technical system while users input data into a user-friendly front-end. Additionally, the system can recognize information required for different functions but is useful for the same instance, e.g., information from different individuals and job functions related to one field visit.

4.2 Secure communications

Good information and skillful communication are vital for the coordination of relief and response efforts. Overall, secure information and communication can enhance operations. In the absence of such systems, or in case their coverage is patchy, the iTRACK communications system can establish secure information and communication channels for humanitarian operations in times of conflict.

4.3 Navigation and routing

Navigation enables the pinpointing of staff and other commodities; this information can then be used for routing. The use of more advanced iTRACK navigation and routing tools and techniques can lead to more precise locational information of staff and assets. In combination with real-time sensing and tracking as well as logistics decision support, decisions are based on real-time safety information of staff and location of commodities. For instance, in cases where multiple organizations are contracted to provide goods to one location, technology can be used to determine the suitability and availability of products. Although current routing is primarily pre-planned, due to the volatility of conflict zones, dynamic routing possibilities are desirable.

4.4 Real-time threat detection

Humanitarian organization staff sometimes operates in areas where real-time threat detection is vital for successfully carrying out their mandate. Additionally, different countries have different threat profiles.

However, some of the biggest risks faced by humanitarian personnel in conflict zones include kidnapping, being ambushed, bombing, mob violence, and shooting. Co-ordination mechanisms in the humanitarian supply network, across humanitarian organizations and their local contacts and implementing partners is instrumental in threat detection. Furthermore, the experience of staff and communications between mobile and stationary entities can be used for warnings and in logistical decision-making. The iTRACK system can integrate different locations and organizations thus enhancing threat detection. Apart from the experience of staff, threat detection to date is mainly dependent on functioning communications.

4.5 Logistics decision support

Logistics is an essential tool in humanitarian operations of any kind. The procurement, storage, tracking and transportation of goods is a vital part of relief and response operations. Many logistical decisions for humanitarian operations in conflict zones are made in support and staging areas (especially procurement of goods but also the contracting of logistics service providers), often with only operational activities and decisions taking place in the conflict zone. Most humanitarian organizations use their own logistics information systems (LIS) for their operations. Visibility beyond the organization and the organizations' staff and vehicles are often reduced to the information from waybills, except commodity tracking for specific commodities (e.g., due to quality control in the cold chain of vaccines). Operational decisions in the conflict zone would primarily benefit from an integration of all the components in the iTRACK system.

Further Reading

iTRACK. (2017). D2.4. Humanitarian Logistics Policies & Case Brief [Online]
https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_WP2_D2.4%E2%80%93%20Humanitarian%20Logistics%20Policies%20&%20Case%20Brief.pdf

4 The iTRACK Components

4.1 iTRACK user system roles

Each user of the iTRACK system takes a specific role within the system after they log in. Their function within the organization determines their role. Table 2 lists common job titles of humanitarian organizations and their respective roles in the iTRACK system. Each role has access to a particular subset of functionalities within the system. Depending on the different staff functions, and their respective roles with the system, users are exposed to various decision dilemmas in certain situations.

Table 2. List of common job titles of humanitarian organizations and their respective roles in the iTRACK system

Staff function within an organization		iTRACK system role
Internal	Mission leader	Mission Leader
	Convoy Leader	
	Logistics officer	Logistics Officer
	Logistics manager	
	Warehouse manager	Warehouse Manager / Transporter
	Warehouse manager	
	Warehouse assistant / Asset manager	
	Transportation manager	
	Distribution manager	Distribution Manager
	Delivery manager	
	Information management officer	Information Management Officer
	IMO	
	Data Coordinator	
	GIS specialist	
	Security Officer, Security Officer 1 & 2	Security Officer
	Assessment & monitoring support	Control Room Operator
	IM focal points	Information Observer
Filed worker	Field Worker	
External	Local transportation	Field Worker / Vehicle Driver / Limited Access Field Worker
	Local warehouse	Field worker / limited access field worker
	Local security	
	Local NGOs	
	Driver	Vehicle driver
	Local government	N/A
	Local communities	N/A

4.2 iTRACK Components

Generally, the iTRACK system components can be divided into frontend apps (mobile applications used by field personnel), backend applications (software that is used in organizations' control centers) and the technical components mounted into convoy vehicles (for continuous threat detection and decision support). These components are implemented via the iTRACK solutions briefly explained in this section. Table 3 gives an overview of the technical components of the iTRACK system. In these technical components, user roles have different levels of access to data and functions.

Table 3. An overview of the technical components of the iTRACK system

#	Group	Description
1	iTRACK mobile application	This component group refers to the iTRACK personnel and logistics mobile applications <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tracking of individuals and assets
2	iTRACK system	This group refers to all technical components that form the iTRACK system <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Secure messaging Real-time threat detection Alerts and decision support Social Media monitoring Storage of data
3	Onboard iTRACK app	Refers to the onboard application installed on the onboard smart devices
4	iTRACK application	Refers to the application offered at the backend <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Data visualization of tracked assets and personnel Decision support for logistics planning

SocialSense: is mainly active in the backend. It collects data from social media, including Facebook, Instagram and Twitter, and analyses the data to detect potential threats for specific areas. Identified threats can be sent to the apps of field personnel (Figure 2).

Figure 1 The overview of the SocialSense component.

StaffSense: is available to both, field personnel and the command center. It is the main component for tracking individuals, i.e., staff. Users can report threats they encounter and also review already reported threats via StaffSense (Figure 3). The component has a messaging functionality through which staff and control center can exchange information. Field personnel being immediately threatened can activate the panic button of the StaffSense app (Figure 3). This triggers an alert that is immediately sent to the Decision Support Engine in the control center.

Figure 2 Three example screens for the StaffSense app for field personnel. Left: a user reports a threat, center and right: activation of the panic button.

Decision Support Engine: also available to both, field personnel and command center (Figure 4). The component is used to plan the route of a convoy. It stores the details of the convoy mission, e.g., what assets are being transported, or what personnel is part of the convoy. In the case the command center or mission head decides to deviate from the planned route, the decision support engine helps in re-routing.

Figure 3 The Decision Support Engine. Left: an overview of the command center. Right: mobile app used by field personnel.

Vehicle mounted devices: only available to field personnel. These devices are fixed. They are installed in a vehicle of the convoy (Figure 5). The camera scans the vehicle's environment, and the real-time threat detection component assesses the camera footage for potential threats. In case of detected threats, alerts are sent to StaffSense and the Decision Support Engine.

Figure 4 Vehicle-mounted devices for real-time threat detection.

QR app: only available to field personnel. The app is used for example by warehouse staff to scan the QR codes of incoming and outgoing commodities (Figure 6). The information is sent to the Decision Support Engine so that the organization can keep track of the movement of commodities.

The **onboard threat detection** component provides real-time alerts to convoy members and headquarters to allow and support rapid threat response and decision making. A **camera** mounted on a convoy vehicle records panoramic views around the vehicle and sends the video stream to the threat detection software. If threats are identified, real-time alerts are sent to **iTRACK mobile apps** and the **decision support engine**. All recorded data is temporarily stored during the mission.

The threat detection component analyses the threat in real-time and immediately purges the data after the analysis is complete. A threat, reported by a field personnel via StaffSense, is verified by an authorized user (mission head, security officer) via the Decision Support Engine (the reported threat pops up on the map, and the authorized user clicks on it, checks it and decides whether to verify it). Once the threat is verified, and the analysis is completed, the data is destroyed. Nevertheless, the continuous operation of the camera might record confidential information, which might cause conflicts with external parties. Moreover, as the installation of the mounted devices is fixed, transferring the system to another vehicle takes a considerable amount of time.

Communication and information exchange between convoy and headquarters can be conducted continuously through the system's **messaging** component. The conversations are monitored through the **pattern-recognition** component to detect potential threats, automatically. By default, messages that are transmitted through StaffSense are transmitted **securely** via **encrypted** communication channels. However, this can be turned off, for example, to abide by certain government policies that might deny encrypted communication.

Figure 5 Scanning assets through their QR codes.

Headquarters can continuously monitor various information streams, including **news** and **social media**, and assess the likelihood of potential threats in certain areas through the **decision support engine**. This allows for the identification of rumors and messages of distress near locations the convoy is planned to go.

A convoy member who perceives an immediate threat can activate the **panic button**. Thus, a panic report is immediately sent to the headquarters including the geolocation of the user. Regardless of whether or not a panic alert was sent, the **tracking** component transmits users' location as soon as a convoy starts its mission and moves along the planned route.

Further Reading

iTRACK. (2019). D6.4. Final Demo Design [Online] https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK%20WP6%20TUD%20D6.4%20-%20Final%20Demo%20Design_v2.pdf

5 Humanitarian Information Management Policies

5.1 The Four Guiding Humanitarian Principles

Building on the United Nations efforts on a human-rights-based approach to humanitarian response, humanitarian activities should be guided by the four principles: humanity, neutrality, impartiality, and independence. The first three principles have been endorsed in the General Assembly resolution 46/182; later in 2004, the General Assembly resolution 58/114 added independence as a fourth fundamental principle that guides humanitarian assistance. The four principles that most humanitarian organizations committed to are:

HUMANITARIAN PRINCIPLES

Humanity: human suffering must be addressed wherever it is found. The purpose of humanitarian action is to protect life and health and ensure respect of human beings.

Neutrality: humanitarian actors must not take sides in hostilities or engage in controversies of a political, racial, religious or ideological nature.

Impartiality: humanitarian action must be carried out on the basis of need alone, giving priority to the most urgent cases of distress and making no distinctions on the basis of nationality, race, gender, religious belief, class or political opinions.

Independence: humanitarian action must be autonomous from the political, economic, military or other objectives that any actor may hold concerning areas where humanitarian action is being implemented.

5.2 Humanitarian IM best practices

By following best practices in the use of information, humanitarian organizations can improve their information management. At the Global Symposium +5 in Geneva in 2007, representatives of humanitarian actors reviewed and amended a list of principles of humanitarian information management and exchange. The 2002 symposium eventually endorsed these principles and to date have been republished and updated several times. The best practices in humanitarian information management and exchange reflect the humanitarian imperative to assist affected and at-risk populations by adhering to the described humanitarian principles. The humanitarian IM best practices strive to support humanitarian organizations to achieve more effective humanitarian intervention. The guiding principles identified by the information professionals in the humanitarian community can be found in Annex B.

In addition to this standard reference, several other operational guidelines for information management have been formulated by many different humanitarian organizations. Here, we limit the analysis to publications by UN agencies. First, the On-Site Operations Coordination Centre (OSOCC) guidelines were created to instruct OCHA field workers to implement the four OSOCC system components: Virtual OSOCC, Reception Departure Centre, OSOCC, and Sub-OSOCC. The document is very comprehensive and contains detailed guidance notes and resources.

Second, the United Nations Disaster Assessment and Coordination (UNDAC) Field Handbook (OCHA 2013) serves as a guide for UNDAC team members before and during the humanitarian response. Concerning IM, the handbook provides instructions for the UNDAC team to build the operational picture of the field situation during the mission cycle. A typical mission cycle consists of pre-mission, on-mission activities, and mission end. The responsibilities of the UNDAC team in these three stages are specified. The handbook provides performance indicators and specifications for each step in the IM process.

Third, the Inter-Agency Standing Committee (IASC) provides an Operational Guidance on Responsibilities of Cluster / Sector Leads & OCHA in Information Management, which comprise of detailed country-level guidance to ensure that relevant information related to a humanitarian emergency reaches the right person at the right time, in a usable form. Eventually, the information disseminated should facilitate humanitarian aid workers to understand the situations and to make right and timely decisions.

In addition to general standards for information management practice, country-specific guidelines have been drafted, which consider the specific local context. For example, the strategic response plan for Typhoon Haiyan was explicitly made to support the government of the Philippines' response to the immediate humanitarian needs of the disaster. This response plan includes an IM handbook, to guide the implementation of the humanitarian IM principles.

5.3 Inherent Contradictions in the Current Humanitarian IM best practices

The outlined best practice guidelines are quite broad and unspecific and therefore do not provide field workers with detailed guidance on what to do in certain situations. On the other hand, humanitarian organizations are diverse, and therefore it is impossible to provide a template for IM practices that would fit all organizations.

The presented recommendations address several issues that are important to information management in the humanitarian context. However, there is an inherent contradiction between various principles and trade-offs need to be made on many of the depicted elements, for instance, between timeliness and verifiability of information as well as inclusiveness and confidentiality. Confidentially implies limited access to information because listings of personal details could endanger lives. Nevertheless, inclusiveness implies the sharing of data with external organizations and data storages, etc. The imperative to collaborate must be balanced with the responsibility not to harm the wellbeing of aid workers. Consequently, humanitarian organizations need to openly assess and balance the criticality of additional use cases with the responsibility to uphold privacy and security concerns. A benefit in planning and coordination is no blanket waiver to collect, analyze and disseminate information without considering their associated risks.

The humanitarian IM principles introduced in this section provides generic and standard guidelines on handling information exchange in humanitarian missions. These policy guidelines do not distinguish specific contexts of field situations, whereas iTRACK is concerned with conflict zones and demands corresponding IM policies in times of conflict. In order to further generate IM policies for conflict zones concerning iTRACK missions, the IM decision dilemmas and policy guidelines are discussed in the next section.

Further Reading

iTRACK. (2017). D2.3. Humanitarian IM Policies & Case Briefs [Online]
https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_WP2_D2.3_Humanitarian%20IM%20Policies_FINAL.pdf

6 Humanitarian Information Management in Conflicts

In times of conflict, humanitarian organizations are faced with decision dilemmas and have to make trade-offs [e.g., it is not clear whether to proceed with a mission after receiving rumors or messages that the place is not safe]. This handbook provides a general policy guidance to help iTRACK users to address these decision dilemmas.

There were ten decision dilemmas identified in a Policy Workshop held on the 14th to the 15th January 2019, in Delft, The Netherlands. Some of the dilemmas focused on Humanitarian Information Management in Conflicts and others on the ethical and safe usage of iTRACK solutions. After the January workshop, a questionnaire was developed and disseminated widely during 2019 Humanitarian Network Partnership Week (HNPW) in Geneva, Switzerland on the 4th to the 8th of February 2019. Part of the guideline contains insights drawn from the results obtained during HNPW in Geneva, Switzerland. Each of the three Humanitarian Information Management in Conflicts decision dilemmas are addressed separately in this section.

The three identified dilemmas that humanitarian organizations may face relating to humanitarian information management issues in conflict are:

1. How do you deal with accidentally recorded or filmed confidential information, e.g., on cases of gender-based violence?
2. Should you use encryption in the iTRACK system when it conflicts with government policy?
3. What should you do when the convoy consists of different organizations with different policies and standards?

Each discussion of a specific decision dilemma contains a list of generic guidance and a checklist of actions that the humanitarian organization can use to check progress. The subsequent session (section 8) focuses on the ethical and safe usage of iTRACK dilemmas, faced by the iTRACK team in times of conflict. Four decision dilemmas were not addressed in this handbook, but are provided in Annex C.

6.1 Accidentally recorded or filmed confidential information

Table 4. Dilemma 1 – How to deal with accidentally received confidential information

Dilemma	How do you deal with accidentally recorded or filmed confidential information, e.g., on cases of gender-based violence?
Decision Options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Destroy: You should immediately destroy the information because its use conflicts with Privacy Laws. ▪ Use for safety reasons: You use it to inform staff about higher risk zones. Staff safety is more important than Privacy Laws ▪ Use for humanitarian reasons: The information is needed to protect beneficiaries.
Questionnaire Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Use for safety reasons: You use it to inform staff about higher risk zones. Staff safety is more important than Privacy Laws
Policy Considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ If there is a legal basis for retaining accidentally recorded and filmed information, then the information can be used to inform decision-making, for instance, whether to send a convoy to a high-risk zone. ▪ The probable legal basis for using confidential information is ‘legitimate interests.’ ▪ Legitimate interests override data subject fundamental rights and freedoms and interests. These interests can be the humanitarian organizations’ interests, the interest of the convoy on a particular mission or societal interests (the beneficiaries). ▪ Before relying on ‘legitimate interests’ to process accidentally recorded confidential information, you should identify a valid, legitimate interest, demonstrate that processing the confidential information is necessary, and finally balance the interest against the individual’s fundamental rights, freedoms, and interests. ▪ Also, there is a need to demonstrate that it was necessary to process the accidentally recorded or filmed confidential information. This can be done by clearly explaining that there is no other less intrusive way to attain the results. ▪ Legitimate interests should be balanced with individual interests. This process is referred to as legitimate interest’s assessment (LIA). If the data processing results in unjustified harm, then the humanitarian organization’s legitimate interest will most likely be overridden by the individual interest. ▪ Moreover, if there is a legal basis for processing the data, the individual should be informed that their confidential data will be processed, the purpose for processing the data, the data retention period, and who will receive the information. ▪ Finally, a record of the LIA should be securely stored, to enable your organization to demonstrate compliance, if the need arises.
Further Reading	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ ICO. <i>Legitimate Interests</i>. [Online] https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-data-protection/guide-to-the-general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr/lawful-basis-for-processing/legitimate-interests/ ▪ <i>iTRACK (2018), D2.8, Humanitarian IM Policies and Case Briefs</i>. [Online] https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_WP2_D2.8_Humanitarian%20IM%20Policies_final.pdf ▪ <i>iTRACK (2018), D3.2, Socio-cultural considerations for future development</i>, [Online] https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_D3.2%20Socio-cultural%20considerations%20for%20future%20development_Final.pdf

iTRACK Guidelines on the use of confidential information for legitimate interests

Table 5. Dilemma 1 – iTRACK Guidelines on the use of confidential information for legitimate interests

Modified from: ICO. *Legitimate Interests*. [Online] <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-data-protection/guide-to-the-general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr/lawful-basis-for-processing/legitimate-interests/>

- 1 Before deciding to process the confidential information, you must be confident that your legitimate interests are not overridden by the risks you have identified.
- 2 Maintain records of your LIA and the outcome to document your reasoning and demonstrate that the decision was made using proper decision-making processes to justify the outcome.
- 3 The humanitarian organization's LIA must be regularly reviewed, to assess whether there are significant changes in the purpose of processing the confidential information, or the context has changed, or the nature of the circumstances.
- 4 The confidential information should not be processed or should be processed under another legal basis if there is lack of clarity in the balancing test outcome.
- 5 In cases where the LIA indicates significant risks to the individual, then your humanitarian organization should consider undertaking a Data Privacy Impact Assessment (DPIAs) to assess the risks associated with the use of confidential personal data and suggest potential risk mitigation strategies.
- 6 People in the confidential information must be informed that the accidentally recorded or filmed confidential information will be processed while relying on legitimate interests, and precisely what these interests are.
- 7 Newly acquired, accidentally recorded or filmed confidential information, can be processed using the previous LIA, if you can demonstrate that the previous purpose is the same as the current purpose. However, if time allows, it is beneficial to conduct a fresh LIA, to counter-check whether the two instances are compatible.
- 8 Once the data subject has been informed, if they exercise their right to object, then you must stop processing the data unless you can demonstrate that your legitimate interest is compelling enough to override the data subject's rights and freedoms.
- 9 When the use of the accidentally recorded or filmed confidential information is compelling enough to override the data subject's rights and freedoms, and there is a pressing need for its use, it should then be used in the most effective way to support humanitarian staff safety, public safety and law enforcement with the aim of processing recordings, images and information of evidential value.
- 10 The confidential information will only be retained long enough for any incident to come to light (e.g., for the hijack of humanitarian staff to be noticed) and the incident to be investigated.
- 11 There should be effective review mechanisms to ensure compliance with national and international legal requirements, policies and standards, and regular review reports should be published.

Table 6. Dilemma 1 – Checklist on the use of confidential information for legitimate interests**CHECKLIST**

Modified from: ICO. Legitimate Interests. [Online] <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-data-protection/guide-to-the-general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr/lawful-basis-for-processing/legitimate-interests/>

- We understand our responsibility to protect the individual's interests.
- We have identified the relevant, legitimate interests, conducted an LIA and kept a record of it, to ensure that we can justify our decision.
- We have checked that the processing is necessary and there is no less intrusive way to achieve the same result.
- We have done a balancing test, and are confident that the individual's interests do not override those legitimate interests.
- We only use individuals' data in ways they would reasonably expect unless we have a good reason.
- We are not using people's data in ways they would find intrusive or which could cause them harm, unless we have a very good reason.
- The confidential information will only be retained long enough for any incident to come to light and the incident to be investigated.
- Except for law enforcement bodies, the confidential information will not be provided to third parties.
- If we process children's data, we take extra care to make sure we protect their interests.
- We have considered whether we can offer an opt out.
- If our LIA identifies a significant privacy impact, we have considered whether we also need to conduct a DPIA.
- We keep our LIA under review and repeat it, if circumstances change.

6.2 When iTRACK encryption conflicts with government policy

Table 7. Dilemma 2 – What to do when the iTRACK encryption conflicts with government policy

Dilemma	Should you use encryption in the iTRACK system when it conflicts with government policy?
Decision Options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Use for sensitive data: You should use encryption because we need to protect our sensitive data. ▪ Use to protect staff: You should use encryption because it provides more security for our staff. ▪ Not use: You should avoid conflict with government policy so that they can facilitate access to the beneficiaries.
Questionnaire Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Use for sensitive data: You should use encryption because we need to protect our sensitive data. ▪ Use to protect staff: You should use encryption because it provides more security for our staff.
Policy Considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The data encryption layer and the messaging gateway is the ‘physical’ defense and protection of secure communication in the iTRACK system. ▪ Message exchange in iTRACK is secured by decryption/encryption mechanism and messaging gateway. The information goes into the iTRACK platform can be generally grouped into three data categories: device id/user credentials, personal data and vehicle/ assets data. The information that comes out of iTRACK platform can be generally grouped into three data categories: device/user token, alerts, and routes. ▪ When data encryption conflicts with government policy, your humanitarian organization could argue that data encryption is necessary, using the ‘vital interests’ or the ‘special category data’ as your lawful basis. ▪ Vital interest only applies if the personal data needs to be encrypted for the protection of someone’s life. ▪ The ‘special category data’ includes information on race; ethnic origin; politics; religion; sex life; or sexual orientation, which if accessed by a third party may pose significant risks on the humanitarian staff’s fundamental rights and freedoms. ▪ Before proceeding to use encryption, you should consider whether you are likely to rely on the ‘vital interests’ or the ‘special category data’ arguments to support your decision. ▪ Your decision should be documented and justifiable to the government.
Further Reading	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ ICO. <i>Encryption</i>. [Online] https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-data-protection/encryption/ ▪ <i>iTRACK (2018), D2.8, Humanitarian IM Policies and Case Briefs</i>. [Online] https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_WP2_D2.8_Humanitarian%20IM%20Policies_final.pdf ▪ <i>iTRACK (2018), D3.2, Socio-cultural considerations for future development</i>, [Online] https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_D3.2%20Socio-cultural%20considerations%20for%20future%20development_Final.pdf ▪ <i>iTRACK. (2017), D2.3, Humanitarian IM Policies and Case Briefs</i>. [Online] https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_WP2_D2.3_Humanitarian%20IM%20Policies_FINAL.pdf

iTRACK IM Guidelines on Data Encryption

Table 8. _ 2 – iTRACK IM Guidelines on Data Encryption

Modified from: ICO. *Encryption*. [Online] <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-data-protection/encryption/> and *CCTV filming carried out by others. pp. 41-42* [Online] <https://ico.org.uk/for-the-public/cctv/>

- 1 In countries where encryption is restricted, when the use of iTRACK encryption is in pursuit of vital interests or the data falls within the special category data, and there is a pressing need for its collection and processing, it should then be discussed with the relevant government authorities and an agreement reached on data encryption, if possible.
- 2 There should be an effective data encryption review mechanism to ensure compliance with national and international legal requirements, policies and standards, and regular reports should be published.
- 3 Clear rules, policies, and procedures must be in place to govern how and when encryption is implemented before the iTRACK encryption is used, and these must be communicated to all who need to comply with them.
- 4 There must be clear responsibility and accountability for the iTRACK encryption activities including the use of the encrypted information.
- 5 Measures should be taken to safeguard the disclosure or loss of the keys, to protect the encrypted sensitive information from being lost or accessed by the wrong person.
- 6 No more encrypted information should be stored than that which is strictly required for the stated purpose, and such data should be deleted once their purposes have been discharged.
- 7 Access to encrypted information should be restricted, and there must be clearly defined rules on who can gain access and for what purpose such access is granted; the disclosure of encrypted information should only take place when it is necessary for such a purpose or law enforcement purposes.
- 8 The humanitarian organization should be aware of the residual risks of encryption and have steps in place to address these.
- 9 Encrypted data should be subject to appropriate security measures to safeguard against unauthorized access and use.
- 10 Data encryption user authorization for configuration should be restricted, and there must be clearly defined rules on who can gain access to authorize implementation of data encryption and for what purpose.
- 11 Additional checks should be placed on super-users' (have access to the security layer) behavior to ensure that the encrypted information remains secure.
- 12 Any encrypted information used to support the iTRACK system should be accurate and kept up to date.
- 13 Staff should be trained on the importance of data encryption, what data should be encrypted, how and when to use it and how to keep the sensitive information secure.

Table 9. Dilemma 2 – Checklist on Data Encryption**CHECKLIST**

Modified from: ICO. Encryption. [Online] <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-data-protection/encryption/>

- We have an appropriate policy in place governing our use of encryption.
- The problem we are trying to address has been clearly defined, and data encryption is the best solution. This decision should be reviewed regularly.
- We understand that encryption can be an appropriate technical measure to ensure that we process personal data securely.
- We have in place an effective data encryption review mechanism to ensure compliance with national and international legal requirements.
- We train our staff on the use and importance of encryption.
- We have assessed the nature and scope of our processing activities and have implemented encryption solution(s) to protect the personal data we store and/or transmit.
- We understand the residual risks that remain, even after we have implemented our encryption solution(s).
- We have established clear responsibilities and accountabilities for the iTRACK encryption activities.
- We have developed appropriate security measures to safeguard against unauthorized access and use of encrypted data.
- We have restricted the authorization of encryption, and have clearly defined rules on who can gain access to authorize implementation of data encryption.
- We ensure that the encrypted information is accurate and kept up to date.
- Regular checks are carried out to ensure that data encryption is working properly.

6.3 Convoy consists of organizations with different policies and standards

Table 10. Dilemma 3 – What to do when the organizations in the convoy have different policies and standards

Dilemma	What should you do when the convoy consists of different organizations with different policies and standards?
Decision Options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Consensus: You should consult different sources and make a balanced judgment. ▪ Maximum safety standards: We insist on the highest safety and security policies being respected. ▪ Minimum safety standards: We insist on the lowest common safety and security policies being respected. ▪ Proceed: There is no time to seek consensus or agree on minimum safety standards; we need to proceed urgently.
Questionnaire Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Minimum safety standards: We insist on the lowest common safety and security policies being respected.
Policy Considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Most humanitarian organizations would, in principle, agree to the lowest common safety and security policies being respected. However, the challenge arises when they have to determine what are the minimum standards, in that particular context. ▪ There are many facets to this dilemma, you could assess it from security policies, staff safety policies or personal data protection policies that may enhance staff safety, during the mission. ▪ Since the focus of this handbook is IM policies, the discussion is limited to determining the minimum data security policies aimed at protecting the humanitarian staff on a convoy through securing their personal data. ▪ The convoy consisting of different organizations with different policies and standards is using one iTRACK solution. Thus, these organizations may jointly process personal and sensitive data. However, there is no shared personal and sensitive data protection governance and accountability mechanism. ▪ The guidelines focus on how these humanitarian organizations can introduce the humanitarian IM accountability principle into such a scenario. ▪ The humanitarian IM accountability principle helps different organizations to jointly demonstrate compliance to all the other IM principles, in a particular joint mission and similar (same organizations) future missions. ▪ Most of the recommendations will only apply if there is continued engagement between the different organizations, thus necessitating the establishment of a governance and accountability mechanism. ▪ Accountability builds trust between the different organizations and mitigates enforcement action risks that may arise from their joint mission.
Further Reading	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ ICO. (2018). Accountability and Governance [Online] https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-data-protection/guide-to-the-general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr/accountability-and-governance/ ▪ <i>iTRACK (2018), D2.8, Humanitarian IM Policies, and Case Briefs.</i> [Online] https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_WP2_D2.8_Humanitarian%20IM%20Policies_final.pdf ▪ <i>iTRACK (2018), D3.2, Socio-cultural considerations for future development,</i> [Online] https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_D3.2%20Socio-cultural%20considerations%20for%20future%20development_Final.pdf

iTRACK Accountability Guidelines on a convoy with different policies and standards

Table 11. Dilemma 3 – iTRACK Accountability Guidelines convoy with different policies and standards

Modified from: ICO. (2018). *Accountability and Governance* [Online] <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-data-protection/guide-to-the-general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr/accountability-and-governance/>

- 1 Use of iTRACK solutions by a convoy consists of different organizations with different policies and standards requires minimum compliance with international data protection principles.
- 2 The joint team should establish appropriate organizational and technical measures to comply with the humanitarian IM accountability principle.
- 3 The joint mission should assign a data protection officer (DPO) to continually monitor and provide advice on convoy's compliance with the humanitarian IM principles. If it is not necessary to assign a specific staff, then the convoy should ensure that there is sufficient capacity within the team to ensure compliance.
- 4 Clear reporting structures must be in place before an iTRACK solution is used jointly by the different humanitarian organizations, and these must be communicated to all who need to comply with them.
- 5 The joint mission should establish mechanisms that can detect, assess, document and report personal data breaches while using the iTRACK solutions.
- 6 If the data being processed is likely to harm individual humanitarian staff interests, the team should consider conducting a DPIA, to identify and if possible, minimize the data protection risks.
- 7 Joint security measures (access controls, security policies, recovery plans, and security monitoring) should be in place to ensure that the data being processed using the iTRACK solutions, remains confidential, accessible and maintains integrity.
- 8 The different humanitarian organizations traveling on the same mission should use contracts that outline the liabilities and responsibilities of the different parties when they use a processor to handle their mission staff's personal data on their behalf.
- 9 The joint mission should maintain records of data that has been processed for that particular mission, the purpose of processing the data, information on data retention (if applicable) and data sharing details.
- 10 There should be effective review, and audit mechanism to ensure the mission consisting of different organizations is jointly in compliance with national and international legal requirements, policies and standards, and regular reports should be published.
- 11 If the different organizations will continue to engage in joint missions, there is need to put in place data protection policies for the joint missions. The level of detail will depend on whether the joint mission regularly processes personal data or sensitive information. In cases where sensitive information is processed, the policies should be comprehensive and robust.
- 12 The joint mission should ensure that the humanitarian staff in convoy possess a high level of awareness and understanding of data protection and the humanitarian IM principles.

Table 12. Dilemma 3 – Checklist for enhancing accountability in convoy with different policies and standards**CHECKLIST**

Modified from: ICO. (2018). *Accountability and Governance* [Online] <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-data-protection/guide-to-the-general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr/accountability-and-governance/>

- We take responsibility for complying with the humanitarian IM principles, as a joint mission comprising of multiple organizations with different policies and standards.
- We keep evidence of the steps we take to comply with the accountability principle.
- We have appointed a data protection officer (where necessary).
- We jointly adopt and implement data protection policies (if necessary and where proportionate);
- We have common security measures to ensure that the data being processed using the iTRACK solutions remains confidential, accessible and maintains integrity.
- We have written contracts in place with organizations that process personal data on our behalf.
- We maintain documentation of our processing activities during the joint humanitarian mission.
- We jointly implement appropriate security measures, and not using people's data in ways which could cause them harm, unless we have a very good reason.
- We jointly record and, where necessary, report personal data breaches.
- If necessary, we jointly conduct data protection impact assessments for uses of personal data that are likely to harm individuals' interests severely.
- We jointly review and update our accountability measures at appropriate intervals.
- We have joint training activities to ensure that humanitarian staff in convoy possess a high level of awareness and understanding of data protection.

7 Ethical and Safe Usage of iTRACK Solutions

Before iTRACK solutions were developed, the project developed user and technology requirements, based on detailed market and policy research. One key outcome of the studies was the development of a list of No-go areas for iTRACK. No-go areas are acceptable thresholds, when implementing the iTRACK system. They were considered at every design step of the iTRACK system. These No-go areas may also apply to organizations who adopt iTRACK solutions. The No-go areas consist of:

1. The laws of the country or countries of operation will be upheld;
2. Specifically, for technology and telecommunications, individual country laws and international standards will be upheld;
3. International humanitarian law will be upheld;
4. The humanitarian do-no-harm principle will be upheld;
5. The humanitarian standards will be upheld;
6. iTRACK is religious, tribal, clan and custom neutral;
7. Specific UN/NGO agency security and other guidelines will be upheld; and
8. Informed consent will be sought from all participants.

However, when implementing iTRACK solutions, there are also ethical considerations that need to be considered. Also, it is important to consider how iTRACK solutions can be safely used. This section discusses three identified dilemmas that humanitarian organizations may face related to ethical and safe usage of iTRACK solutions. These dilemmas are:

1. The iTRACK system requires a camera on board, should you accept the risk of having cameras when traveling to conflict zones?
2. Should you track off-duty staff, in high-risk zones?
3. You have an urgent mission; can you deploy a team quickly even if they are not trained on iTRACK technology?

Each of the decision dilemmas for ethical and safe usage of iTRACK solutions are discussed separately. Also, each discussion of a specific decision dilemma contains a list of generic guidance and a checklist of actions that the humanitarian organization can use to check progress.

Further Reading

iTRACK. (2018). D3.2. Socio-cultural considerations for future development. [Online] https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_D3.2%20Socio-cultural%20considerations%20for%20future%20development_Final.pdf

iTRACK (2018), D2.8, Humanitarian IM Policies, and Case Briefs. [Online] https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_WP2_D2.8_Humanitarian%20IM%20Policies_final.pdf

7.1 Deciding on use of camera onboard when traveling to conflict zones

Table 13. Dilemma 4 – Whether to communicate the use of a camera on board

Dilemma	The iTRACK system requires a camera on board, should you accept the risk of having cameras when traveling to conflict zones?
Decision Options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Reduce risk: You should comply with privacy laws & facilitate information sharing, use, and retrieval. ▪ Accept risk: You use RealTime security footage, and iTRACK does not store data, no consent is needed. ▪ Avoid risk: You should proceed without cameras because the use of cameras may risk staff lives.
Questionnaire Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Reduce risk: You should comply with privacy laws & facilitate information sharing, use, and retrieval.
Policy Considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Using an iTRACK camera in conflict zones is possible, but humanitarian organizations have to ensure that its use is ethical, safe and legitimate. Legitimacy can be assessed based on the reason for using the camera and the current policies and laws. Camera usage can be privacy intrusive. iTRACK system cameras place humanitarian workers under surveillance and record their movements. ▪ To decide whether to use the camera (if the prevailing policies and laws allow its use in that particular circumstance), you should take into account: the nature of the problem you are seeking to address; whether using a camera is justified and an effective solution or other better solutions exist; what is the impact of its use on humanitarian staff traveling in the convoy, and whether in the light of this, its use is a proportionate response to the problem. ▪ Persons in a vehicle with an iTRACK camera have a right to be informed that there is a camera on board. Also, as part of the iTRACK training before a convoy is sent on a mission, the trainer should explain: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Why your organization requires a camera on board; 2. What type/types of data you are collecting and not collecting, with the camera; 3. How long the camera images and data will be stored; 4. Whether the organization may transfer the camera data to third parties, the rationale for the transfer and to whom; 5. The subject’s right to be informed and complain; and 6. How they can contact the humanitarian organization.
Further Reading	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ iTRACK (2018), D3.2, Socio-cultural considerations for future development, [Online] https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_D3.2%20Socio-cultural%20considerations%20for%20future%20development_Final.pdf ▪ ICO. (2015). <i>In the picture: A data protection code of practice for surveillance cameras and personal information</i>. [Online] https://ico.org.uk/media/1542/cctv-code-of-practice.pdf ▪ ICO. (2018). <i>CCTV filming carried out by others</i>. [Online] https://ico.org.uk/for-the-public/cctv/

iTRACK Safe Usage of Camera Guidelines

Table 14. Dilemma 4 – iTRACK Safe Usage of Camera Guidelines

Modified from: ICO. (2015). *In the picture: A data protection code of practice for surveillance cameras and personal information*. [Online] <https://ico.org.uk/media/1542/cctv-code-of-practice.pdf>

- 1 Use of iTRACK cameras must always be for a specified purpose which is in pursuit of a legitimate aim and necessary to meet an identified pressing need.
- 2 The use of iTRACK camera system must take into account its effect on the safety of the humanitarian staff in convoy and their privacy, with regular reviews to ensure its use remains justified.
- 3 There must be as much transparency in the use of iTRACK camera system as possible, including a published contact point for access to information and complaints.
- 4 There must be clear responsibility and accountability for the iTRACK camera system activities including images and information collected, held and used.
- 5 Clear rules, policies, and procedures must be in place before an iTRACK camera system is used, and these must be communicated to all who need to comply with them.
- 6 No more images and information should be stored than that which is strictly required for the stated purpose of an iTRACK camera system, and such images and information should be deleted once their purposes have been discharged.
- 7 Access to retained images and information should be restricted, and there must be clearly defined rules on who can gain access and for what purpose such access is granted; the disclosure of images and information should only take place when it is necessary for such a purpose or law enforcement purposes.
- 8 iTRACK camera system operators should consider any approved operational, technical and competency standards relevant to the iTRACK system and its purpose and work to meet and maintain those standards.
- 9 Images and information obtained from the iTRACK camera system should be subject to appropriate security measures to safeguard against unauthorized access and use.
- 10 There should be effective review and audit mechanisms to ensure national and international legal requirements, policies and standards are complied with in practice, and regular reports should be published.
- 11 When the use of iTRACK camera system is in pursuit of a legitimate aim, and there is a pressing need for its use, it should then be used in the most effective way to support public safety and law enforcement with the aim of processing images and information of evidential value.
- 12 Any information used to support an iTRACK camera system which compares against a reference database for matching purposes should be accurate and kept up to date.

Table 15. Dilemma 4 – Checklist for Humanitarian Organisations that decide to use iTRACK Camera System**CHECKLIST**

Modified from: ICO. (2015). In the picture: A data protection code of practice for surveillance cameras and personal information. [Online]
<https://ico.org.uk/media/1542/cctv-code-of-practice.pdf>

- There is a named individual who is responsible for the operation of the iTRACK camera system.
- The problem we are trying to address has been clearly defined and installing cameras is the best solution. This decision should be reviewed regularly.
- A system has been chosen which produces clear images which the law enforcement bodies (usually the police) can use to investigate crime, and these can easily be taken from the system when required.
- Cameras have been sited so that they provide clear images.
- Cameras have been positioned to avoid capturing the images of persons not involved in the mission.
- There are visible signs showing that the iTRACK camera system is in operation. Where it is not apparent who is responsible for the system contact details are displayed on the sign(s).
- Images from the iTRACK camera system are securely stored, where only a limited number of authorized persons may have access to them.
- The recorded images will only be retained long enough for any incident to come to light and the incident to be investigated.
- Except for law enforcement bodies, images will not be provided to third parties.
- We have identified the potential impact on individuals' privacy and taken into account the use of the iTRACK camera system.
- We know how to respond to individuals making requests for copies of their images. If unsure we know how to seek advice from the relevant national authority, as soon as such a request is made.
- Regular checks are carried out to ensure that the system is working properly and produces high-quality images.

7.2 At the border, the iTRACK vehicle is not allowed entry

Table 16. Dilemma 5 – What to do when your iTRACK vehicle is not allowed entry, at the border

Dilemma	At the border, vehicles with monitoring and tracking equipment are not allowed entry, and we can only continue in local trucks, what do you do?
Decision Options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Minimum Standards: You use our mobile phones for monitoring and tracking and secure communication. Onboard systems (such as cameras) can stay behind. ▪ Abandon: You need the full monitoring and tracking capacity to ensure security for our staff. ▪ Proceed: You should get into the local truck immediately, and not use monitoring, tracking or secure communication tools.
Questionnaire Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Proceed: You should get into the local truck immediately, and not use monitoring, tracking or secure communication tools.
Policy Considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ International humanitarian organizations (UN organizations, INGOs) procure materials but do not always deliver them with their fleet. They may use various third-party service providers (3PSPs) including logistics service providers (LSPs), their national chapters or other humanitarian organizations, or other co-operation partners (CPs) or implementing partners (IPs), in the course of delivery. They may also use their vehicle fleet for delivering commodities; though this is somewhat rare. Commercial logistics service providers, e.g., DHL or Kuehne+Nagel, are used more and more, and the trend is towards increased use of regional and national CPs, also with regards to logistics. ▪ In the case of restricted access in conflict zones, often, materials are handed over and reloaded from the vehicles of international LSPs to vehicles of national LSPs in the process (often at a national border or if crossing lines of conflict). ▪ The use of 3PSPs may restrict the possibilities to require these 3PSPs to use the iTRACK system. Furthermore, in conflict zones, the use of national LSPs may be either a requirement or a way to increase the possibility for a convoy to get through conflict lines. ▪ The Handbook introduces a Data Controller and a Data Processor. A Data Controller is the person or organization who alone or jointly with others determines the purposes and means of the Processing of Personal Data, whereas a Data Processor is the person or organization who processes Personal Data on behalf of the Data Controller. A Third Party is any natural or legal person, public authority, agency or anybody other than the Data Subject, the Data Controller or the Data Processor. ▪ In the event that the iTRACK vehicle cannot proceed beyond the border and the iTRACK system or some of the components, is transferred to a national 3PSPs, in the course of a mission, there is need for a clear understanding of responsibilities and liabilities regarding personal data. ▪ For adequate protection of the data subjects, the two organizations should sign a contract governing the use of the data, under which the International Humanitarian Organization has the power to direct how the data processor uses the data and respects the data protection safeguards required by the Humanitarian Organization. In some cases, the NGO can contract an IT consulting company in order to perform routine maintenance on its IT system in which the data are stored. Also this contractual agreement between the NGO and the IT Company should abide by the contractual agreement the NGO has with the international humanitarian organization. ▪ As iTRACK is a platform that is populated with the data collected by its users, this means that the users of the system should have the appropriate contracts in place regarding the use and processing of personal data, before the usage of iTRACK.
Further Reading	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ iTRACK. (2017). D2.4. Humanitarian Logistics Policies & Case Brief [Online] https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_WP2_D2.4%20%E2%80%93%20Humanitarian%20Logistics%20Policies%20&%20Case%20Brief.pdf ▪ iTRACK (2018), D2.8, Humanitarian IM Policies, and Case Briefs. [Online] https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_WP2_D2.8_Humanitarian%20IM%20Policies_final.pdf ▪ ICO. (2018). Controllers and Processors. [Online] https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-data-protection/guide-to-the-general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr/key-definitions/controllers-and-processors/

iTRACK Guidelines on third-party service providers (3PSPs)

Table 17. Dilemma 5 – iTRACK Guidelines on third-party service providers (3PSPs)

Modified from: ICO. (2018). **Controllers and Processors**. [Online] <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-data-protection/guide-to-the-general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr/key-definitions/controllers-and-processors/>

- 1 iTRACK controllers must use processors that provide sufficient guarantee that they will undertake appropriate measures (organizational and technical) to ensure that the data processing protects the data subjects.
- 2 The collector and processor(s) must enter into a contract that clearly designates the responsibilities and liabilities and ensures compliance to the collector’s data protection policies. This contract details the purpose, duration, and nature of data processing. Furthermore, it also should highlight the type of data, categories of data subjects and the obligations and rights of the controller.
- 2 The processor must only act on the controller’s documented instructions unless required by law to act without such instructions.
- 3 The processor must ensure that people processing the data are subject to a duty of confidence.
- 4 The processor must take appropriate measures to ensure the security of processing.
- 5 The processor must only engage a sub-processor with the controller’s prior authorization and under a written contract.
- 6 The processor must take appropriate measures to help the controller respond to requests from individuals to exercise their rights.
- 7 The processor must assist the controller in meeting its data protection obligations, the notification of personal data breaches and data protection impact assessments
- 8 The processor must delete or return all personal data to the controller (at the controller’s choice) at the end of the contract, and the processor must also delete existing personal data unless the law requires its storage.
- 9 The processor must submit to audits and inspections. The processor must also give the controller whatever information it needs to ensure they are both meet their data protection obligations.
- 10 If a processor uses a sub-processor (e.g., an IT company) to support the processing of personal data, the processor should enter into a written agreement with the sub-processor.
- 11 Before engaging a sub-processor, a processor must get authorization from the controller.
- 12 The contractual terms between the processor and the sub-processor should provide equivalent protection levels to data subjects in relation to personal data. The processor will remain liable to the controller for compliance by all the engaged sub-processors.

Table 18. Dilemma 5 – Checklist for third-party service providers (3PSPs)

CHECKLIST

Modified from: ICO. (2018). *Controllers and Processors*. [Online] <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-data-protection/guide-to-the-general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr/key-definitions/controllers-and-processors/>

iTRACK (2018), D2.8, *Humanitarian IM Policies*, and Case Briefs. [Online] https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_WP2_D2.8_Humanitarian%20IM%20Policies_final.pdf

- There shall be processing of Personal Data or sensitive information that requires protection.
- The Processing of Personal Data is proportionate; the same purpose cannot be achieved in a less intrusive way.
- We have a signed contract with the processor setting out details of the processing including: the subject matter, duration, nature and purpose of processing. We also included in the contract the type and categories of data being processed and our (controller) rights and obligations.
- The processor has agreed to only act on our documented instructions, unless required by law to act without such instructions.
- The processor has agreed to ensure that people processing the data are subject to a duty of confidence.
- The processor has agreed to take appropriate measures to ensure the security of processing.
- The processor has agreed to only engage a sub-processor with our prior authorization and under a written contract.
- The processor has agreed to take appropriate measures to help us respond to requests from individuals seeking to exercise their data protection rights.
- The processor has agreed to assist us in meeting our obligations in relation to the security of processing, the notification of personal data breaches and data protection impact assessments.
- The processor has agreed to delete or return all personal data to us at the end of the contract, and also delete existing personal data unless the law requires its storage.
- The processor has agreed to submit to audits and inspections. The processor has also agreed to provide needed information to ensure we both meet our obligations.

7.3 Deciding on tracking off-duty staff in high-risk zones

Table 19. Dilemma 6 – Whether to track off-duty staff in high-risk zones

Dilemma	Should you track off-duty staff, in high-risk zones?
Decision Options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ No: We should respect staff privacy, while off-duty. ▪ Track: The safety of staff is of primary importance, whether on/off duty. ▪ Track and restrict access: The information may save lives; we can encrypt the information & restrict access.
Questionnaire Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Track and restrict access: The information may save lives; we can encrypt the information & restrict access.
Policy Considerations	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ The system must be introduced in a transparent and open way for humanitarian workers to understand that although they may be tracked by their organizations, it may lead to additional safety and security. ▪ To minimize the risks of tracking off-duty staff in high-risk zones, the humanitarian organization needs to comply with a number of data protection principles. The most apparent principles that need to be considered before iTRACK is used to track off-duty staff are: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lawfulness, fairness and transparency principle 2. Data minimization principle 3. Storage limitation policy ▪ There must be a valid legal basis for tracking off-duty staff, and processing should not contravene current national and international laws. ▪ Data processing should be fair (not misleading, unexpected or cause irreparable harm to the data subjects). ▪ Transparency involves openly, in a clear and honest manner explaining to the data subjects why you need to track them while they are off-duty and what you will use the data for. ▪ The data minimization principle ensures that the data collected while tracking off-duty staff is adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary for relation to the purposes for which you are processing the data. <p>The storage limitation policy ensures that you do not store personal or sensitive data collected while tracking off-duty staff longer than needed.</p>
Further Reading	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ ICO. (2018). Guide to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). [Online] https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-data-protection/guide-to-the-general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr/principles/lawfulness-fairness-and-transparency/ ▪ <i>iTRACK (2018), D2.8, Humanitarian IM Policies, and Case Briefs.</i> [Online] https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_WP2_D2.8_Humanitarian%20IM%20Policies_final.pdf ▪ <i>iTRACK (2018), D3.2, Socio-cultural considerations for future development,</i> [Online] https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_D3.2%20Socio-cultural%20considerations%20for%20future%20development_Final.pdf ▪ <i>iTRACK. (2017), D2.3, Humanitarian IM Policies, and Case Briefs. pp. 52-54</i> [Online] https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_WP2_D2.3_Humanitarian%20IM%20Policies_FINAL.pdf ▪ Rachels, J. (1975). Why privacy is important. In <i>Can Ethics Provide Answers</i> pp. 145 – 153 [Online] http://www.jamesrachels.org/CEPA10.pdf

iTRACK Guidelines on staff privacy and tracking off-duty staff in high-risk zones

Table 20. Dilemma 6 – iTRACK Guidelines on staff privacy and tracking off-duty staff in high-risk zones

Modified from: **Modified from ICO. (2018). Guide to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).** [Online] <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-data-protection/guide-to-the-general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr/principles/lawfulness-fairness-and-transparency/>

- 1 Tracking off-duty staff must always be for a specified purpose which is in pursuit of a legitimate legal basis and necessary to meet an identified pressing need.
- 2 The use of iTRACK off-duty tracking system must take into account its effect on the safety of the humanitarian staff in convoy and their privacy, with regular reviews to ensure its use remains justified.
- 3 There must be as much transparency in the use of iTRACK off-duty tracking system as possible, including a published contact point for access to information and complaints.
- 4 There must be clear responsibility and accountability for the iTRACK off-duty tracking system activities including images and information collected, held and used.
- 5 Clear rules, policies, and procedures must be in place before an iTRACK off-duty tracking system is used, and these must be communicated to all who need to comply with them.
- 6 No images and information should be stored than that which is strictly required for the stated purpose of an iTRACK off-duty tracking system, and such images and information should be deleted once their purposes have been discharged.
- 7 Access to retained images and information should be restricted, and there must be clearly defined rules on who can gain access and for what purpose such access is granted; the disclosure of images and information should only take place when it is necessary for such a purpose or for law enforcement purposes.
- 8 No longer needed personal data should be erased or anonymized to minimize the risk of the data being outdated, inaccurate, irrelevant or excessive.
- 9 Images and information obtained from the iTRACK off-duty tracking system should be subject to appropriate security measures to safeguard against unauthorized access and use.
- 10 There should be effective review and audit mechanisms to ensure that the iTRACK off-duty tracking system complies with national and international legal requirements, policies and standards, and regular reports should be published.
- 11 The humanitarian organisation should develop and implement retention policies or schedules that identify information to be held, the retention purpose and standard retention periods
- 12 Any information used to support the iTRACK off-duty tracking system which compares against a reference database for matching purposes should be accurate, adequate, limited to the data processing purpose, relevant and kept up to date.

Table 21. Dilemma 6 – Checklist on staff privacy and tracking off-duty staff in high-risk zones

CHECKLIST

Modified from: Modified from ICO. (2018). Guide to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). [Online] <https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-data-protection/guide-to-the-general-data-protection-regulation-gdpr/principles/lawfulness-fairness-and-transparency/>

- Lawfulness:** We have identified an appropriate lawful basis (or bases) for our processing.
- Lawfulness:** If we are processing special category data or criminal offense data, we have identified a condition for processing this type of data.
- Lawfulness:** We do not do anything generally unlawful with personal data.
- Fairness:** We have considered how the processing may affect the individuals concerned and can justify any adverse impact.
- Fairness:** We only handle people’s data in ways they would reasonably expect, or we can explain why any unexpected processing is justified.
- Fairness:** We do not deceive or mislead people when we collect their personal data.
- Transparency:** We are open and honest, and comply with the transparency obligations of the right to be informed.
- Data minimization:** We only collect personal data that we need for our specified purposes.
- Data minimization:** We periodically review the data we hold, and delete anything we do not need.
- Data minimization:** We are open and honest, and comply with the transparency obligations of the right to be informed.
- Storage limitation:** We know what personal data we hold and why we need it.
- Storage limitation:** We carefully consider and can justify how long we keep personal data.
- Storage limitation:** We regularly review our information and erase or anonymize personal data when we no longer need it.
- Storage limitation:** We have a policy with standard retention periods where possible, in line with documentation obligations.
- Storage limitation:** We have appropriate processes in place to comply with individuals’ requests for erasure under ‘the right to be forgotten’.
- Storage limitation:** We clearly identify any personal data that we need to keep for public interest archiving, scientific or historical research, or statistical purposes.

8 Conclusion

This policy handbook contains generic guidance to humanitarian information management in conflicts as well as guidelines for ethical and safe usage of the iTRACK solutions. It is a synthesis and consolidation of the IM, logistics and risk management policies that have been developed in T2.2-T2.4 and it also reflects the ethical and privacy considerations from WP1 and WP3. Its primary focus is to identify, discuss and provide policy guidance on key dilemmas that humanitarian organizations may face while implementing the iTRACK system.

In this handbook six decision dilemmas are discussed and generic guidance for humanitarian IM in times of conflict is provided. Section 7 discusses three identified dilemmas that humanitarian organizations may face that relate to humanitarian information management issues in conflict. These decision dilemmas are:

1. How do you deal with accidentally recorded or filmed confidential information, e.g., on cases of gender-based violence?
2. Should you use encryption in the iTRACK system when it conflicts with government policy?
3. What should you do when the convoy consists of different organizations with different policies and standards?

The subsequent session (section 8) focuses on the ethical and safe usage of iTRACK dilemmas, faced by the iTRACK team in times of conflict. Section 8 explains three identified dilemmas, namely:

1. The iTRACK system requires a camera on board, should you accept the risk of having cameras when traveling to conflict zones?
2. Should you track off-duty staff, in high-risk zones?
3. You have an urgent mission; can you deploy a team quickly even if it is not trained on iTRACK technology?

Each of the three decision dilemmas related to humanitarian information management issues in conflict and ethical and safe usage of iTRACK solutions are discussed separately in their respective sections. Also, each discussion of a specific decision dilemma contains a list of generic guidance and a checklist of actions that the humanitarian organization can use to check progress.

These guidelines will be embedded into the training case (T6.5) to ensure their sustainability beyond the iTRACK project.

9 Definition of Terms and Principles

1. **Beneficiaries:** are considered those who are the primary beneficiaries of aid. Beneficiaries as individual rights holders are entitled to essential services and protection against violence and disaster risks.
2. **Do No Harm Principle:** is the overarching principle which guides the work of Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs) and they must abide by at all times during humanitarian missions. It aims to minimize the harm (physical or psychological) humanitarian actors may cause through their presence. This includes doing no harm to staff, witnesses, local communities, intermediaries and any other person involved including humanitarian actors themselves.
3. **Humanitarian assistance:** any action intended to alleviate suffering, save lives, maintain human dignity, prevent future occurrences and strengthen preparedness during and after natural disasters. This action must be guided by the key humanitarian principles which include humanity, impartiality, neutrality, and independence.
4. **Humanitarian logistics:** The process of planning, implementing and controlling the efficient, cost-effective flow and storage of goods and materials as well as related information, from the point of origin to the point of consumption for the purpose of meeting the end beneficiary's requirements.
5. **Protection of Personal Data:** of both beneficiaries and humanitarian workers is often extremely important in order to safeguard their lives, dignity and privacy of both beneficiaries and humanitarian workers. This is contained in Article 8 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights which states: "1. Everyone has the right to the protection of personal data concerning him or her. 2. Such data must be processed fairly for specified purposes and on the basis of the consent of the person concerned or some other legitimate basis laid down by law. Everyone has the right of access to data which has been collected concerning him or her, and the right to have it rectified. 3. Compliance with these rules shall be subject to control by an independent authority." The EU's Data Protection Directive (95/46/EC) also contain similar provisions, and General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) is also an important document with regard to personal data protection measures in the European Union.
6. **Safety and Security:** The term safety may be defined as a state in which an individual is free from physical and/or psychological harm and therefore, protected. Security are the steps or mechanisms put in place to achieve this state of protection (e.g., a safety barrier). These terms are inextricably linked as without security there is no safety.
7. **The principle of informed consent:** is also embedded in international legislation such as the GDPR and plays an important role in supporting privacy. When documenting information about serious human rights violations, unofficial investigators must strive to do no harm or to minimize the harm they may be inadvertently causing through their presence or mandate. This includes, gaining proper and informed consent from all victims and witnesses prior to being interviewed, externally examined, photographed, having their information recorded, being referred to any support services, or having their information and contact details shared with third parties. It is, therefore important to consider this principle carefully when introducing new technologies which often collect personal data and thus have privacy implications. However, this consideration may differ in times of crises. In fact, the collection of data may be of 'vital interest' in which case; the processing is necessary to protect someone's life. Or it may be a 'public task' in which the processing of data is necessary to perform a task in the public interest or for an official function, and the task or function has a clear basis in law.

Thus, informed consent may not be necessary but what remains important is that the most appropriate lawful basis has been carefully considered, documented and applied.

8. **The Principle of Non-discrimination:** Article 21 of the European Charter of Fundamental Rights prohibits “Any discrimination based on any ground such as sex, race, colour, ethnic or social origin, genetic features, language, religion or belief, political or any other opinion, membership of a national minority, property, birth, disability, age or sexual orientation.” When analyzing new technologies, non-discrimination is particularly important as many profiling technologies have raised a host of ethical, legal and other issues including privacy, equality, due process, safety, security, and liability. This is due to the fact that they can be by their very nature discriminatory tools, as they allow for social categorization and segmentation.
9. **The Principle of Proportionality:** goes hand in hand with the Do No Harm Principle by assessing whether an act is appropriate to its pursued aim and proportionate to the risk associated with it. The Do No Harm Principle and the Principle of Proportionality, therefore, should be at the basis of policy consideration implementing iTRACK, with regard to non-maleficence (not to harm or to inflict the least possible harm to be able to reach a positive outcome).

Further reading

iTRACK. (2018). D3.2. Socio-cultural considerations for future development. pp. 17-23 [Online] https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_D3.2%20Socio-cultural%20considerations%20for%20future%20development_Final.pdf

10 Relevant iTrack Documents

Table 22 contains other iTRACK project information should you consider.

Table 22. A general overview of relevant iTRACK project documents and their online location

Number	Document Name	Document Purpose	Website URL
D9.4	iTRACK project website	A public website has been set up to present information about the iTRACK project, the latest developments and achievements, share important results. The public website contains an overview of the project, its work plan and expected results, details of consortium members, news & updates, articles, and contact information.	https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_WP9_D9.4%E2%80%93First%20Online%20version%20of%20the%20iTRACK%20project%20website.pdf
D3.1	iTRACK impact assessment and recommendations	This document is the ethical and privacy impact assessment (E/PIA) report for the iTRACK project (D3.1). The E/PIA fills a knowledge vacuum on how iTRACK was developed to ensure it abides by and protects, ethics and privacy. By carrying out the E/PIA specifically for iTRACK, privacy and ethics were considered, in the relevant context; namely considering the nature of the situation and context in which the technology will be used as well as the technology itself.	https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_WP3_DEL3.1_EPIA_R01.pdf
D2.3	Humanitarian Information Management Policies & Case Brief	The document reviews the humanitarian information management (IM) principles and best practices and provides the humanitarian IM policy brief for conflict situations.	https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_WP2_D2.3_Humanitarian%20IM%20Policies_FINAL.pdf
D2.4	Humanitarian Logistics Policies & Case Brief	The document provides an overview of humanitarian logistics in conflict zones, thus illustrates the material flows of aid deliveries, both when it comes to commodities, and staff. Importantly, it goes to show how many organizations may be involved in delivery, from material suppliers, to third-party logistics service providers, co-operation and implementation partners, as well as providers of various other services (distribution, monitoring, and evaluation, information, etc.). This myriad of organizations involved makes tracking and tracing particularly challenging, and the more so when talking about conflict zones. The data extends to the various facets of humanitarian aid operations in conflict zones, not just in the different options of own convoys vs. third parties, but also, in terms of simple, one road environments – that significantly simplify not just routing but also tracking – to technically challenging demilitarised zones.	https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_WP2_D2.4%E2%80%93%20Humanitarian%20Logistics%20Policies%20&%20Case%20Brief.pdf
D8.1.	Market Analysis	This is a report of the current situation of the market and some estimation regarding its size. It also examines the existing technology solutions and iTRACK's competition and points out iTRACK's competitive advantage. It also contains some elements that should be addressed during the next steps of the project regarding iTRACK's exploitation and go-to-market strategy.	https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_WP8_D8.1_Market_Analysis_and_tech_nology_foresight_FINAL.pdf
D8.2	Report on current practices and Policies	The report initially deals with how the Humanitarian Industry is coordinated, structured, internally governed and who are the most important actors in this framework – in terms of state and non-state organizations. It also presents	https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_WP8_D8.2_Report%20on%20current%20practices%20and%20

Number	Document Name	Document Purpose	Website URL
		the current state of Humanitarian Safety and Security in the Industry and how iTRACK compares to existing solutions. Furthermore, this report analyses the existing policies and regulation affecting humanitarian aid and the tracking and monitoring of humanitarian workers concerning international laws and regulations. It also presents a more in-depth analysis of E.U. laws and regulations, current and upcoming which will affect iTRACK both due to its humanitarian and data-driven nature.	Policies_%20R06_final.pdf
D8.3	Report on SWOT analysis	This report is useful if you want to learn more about the market for humanitarian aid security. The analysis indicates that the market is experiencing intense growth rates and new competitors are emerging. At the same time, NGOs have begun to show greater interest in the security of people in the field and other parties that constitute a humanitarian mission. This trend has led to the creation of several solutions in the last decade that have different components, costs and a varying degree of satisfaction of the needs of organizations.	https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_WP8_D8.3_SWOT%20Analysis_R05_final.pdf
D8.4	Report on Marketing & Positioning Recommendations	The report contains the iTRACK project marketing and positioning research that informed the delivery of state-of-the-art solutions for helping humanitarian aid agencies complete their mission while keeping their personnel, vehicles, and assets safe. The insights are based on desk research and field observations.	https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK%20-%20D8.4%20E2%80%93%20Report%20on%20Marketing%20and%20Positioning%20Recommendations.pdf
D6.6	Scenario generator	This document explains the creation of the scenario-based training and simulation environment for humanitarian operations in high-risk regions.	https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK%20-%20D6.6%20E2%80%93%20Scenario%20Generator.pdf
D2.6	Policies for contingency planning & Case Brief	The report contains a repository of precautionary and responsive recommended actions, (in the format of Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) and policies, was developed based on reviewing existing best practices, security training programs, and interview with subject matter experts from the field. From there, a set of case briefs was developed based on scenarios of missions taking place in conflict zones and address the link between iTRACK system components and such situations.	https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_WP2_D2.6_Policies%20for%20Contingency%20Planning%20and%20Case%20Brief_R2.pdf
D2.8	D2.8 – Humanitarian Information Management Policies, & Case Brief	The document aims at enhancing individuals' Personal Data protection, which is an integral part of protecting people's life, integrity and dignity, and especially so during humanitarian crises.	https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_WP2_D2.8_Humanitarian%20IM%20Policies_final.pdf
D3.2	Socio-cultural considerations for future development	This report undertakes an analysis of the social and cultural implications of the use of the iTRACK tool and each of its components namely: StaffSense, DSE, and QR, onboard sensing and threat detection and the use of multiple components.	https://www.itrack-project.eu/media/articles/files/iTRACK_D3.2%20Socio-cultural%20considerations%20for%20future%20development_Final.pdf

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Annexes

Annex A: iTRACK partners

Table 23. iTRACK Partners

iTRACK Partner	Short name	Country
University of Agder	UiA	Norway
Trilateral Research Ltd.	TRI	United Kingdom
Treelogic Telematica Y Logica Racional Para La Empresa Europea Sl	TREELOGIC	Spain
Knowledge Now Ltd.	K-Now	United Kingdom
Teleplan Globe AS	Teleplan	Norway
Svenska Handelshogskolan	HANKEN	Finland
Intrasoft International SA	INTRA	Luxembourg
Teknova AS	TVA	Norway
ARTTIC	ARTTIC	France
Delft University of Technology	TU Delft	Netherlands
United Nations World Food Programme	WFP	Italy
Information Management And Mine Action Programs Inc.	iMMAP	United States

Annex B: Humanitarian IM Principles

HUMANITARIAN IM PRINCIPLES

Accessibility. Humanitarian information and data should be made accessible to all humanitarian actors by applying easy-to-use formats and by translating information into common or local languages when necessary. Information and data for humanitarian purposes should be made widely available through a variety of online and offline distribution channels including the media.

Inclusiveness. Multiple stakeholders, especially representatives of the affected population, should base information management and exchange on a system of collaboration, partnership and sharing with a high degree of participation and ownership.

Interoperability. All sharable data and information should be made available in formats that can be easily retrieved, shared and used by humanitarian organizations.

Accountability. Users must be able to evaluate the reliability and credibility of data and information by knowing its source. Information providers should be responsible to their partners and stakeholders for the content they publish and disseminate.

Verifiability. Information should be accurate, consistent and based on sound methodologies, validated by external sources, and analyzed within the proper contextual framework.

Relevance. Information should be practical, flexible, responsive, and driven by operational needs in support of decision-making throughout all phases of a crisis.

Impartiality. Information managers should consult a variety of sources when collecting and analyzing information to provide varied and balanced perspectives for addressing problems and recommending solutions.

Timeliness. Humanitarian information should be collected, analyzed and disseminated efficiently, and must be kept current.

Sustainability. Humanitarian information and data should be preserved, cataloged and archived, so that it can be retrieved for future use, such as for preparedness, analysis, lessons learned and evaluation. All stakeholders should promote the use of Open Source Software to further enhance access to information in a sustainable way. When possible, post-emergency data should be transitioned to relevant recovery actors and host governments and training provided on its use.

Humanity. Information should never be used to distort, to mislead or to cause harm to affected or at-risk populations and should respect the dignity of victims.

Reliability. Users must be able to evaluate the reliability and credibility of data and information by knowing its source and method of collection. Collection methods should adhere to global standards where they exist to support and reinforce credibility. Reliability is a prerequisite for ensuring validity and verifiability.

Reciprocity. Information exchange should be a beneficial two-way process between the affected communities and the humanitarian community, including affected governments.

Confidentiality. The processing of any personal data shall not be done without the prior explicit description of its purpose and will only be done for that purpose, and after prior informed consent of the individual concerned. Sufficient safeguards must be put in place to protect personal data against loss, unauthorized processing, and other misuse. If sensitive information is publicly disclosed, the sources of such information will not be released when there is a reasonable risk that doing so will affect the security or integrity of these sources.

Annex C: Identified iTRACK Decision Dilemmas Not Addressed in this Handbook

Table 24. Dilemma 7 – Whether to quickly deploy an untrained team

Dilemma	You have an urgent mission; can you deploy a team quickly even if it is not trained on iTRACK technology?
Decision Options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Inform: You should train them first so that they are able to make informed decisions by using iTRACK. ▪ Abandon: You put the staff at risk when engaging untrained iTRACK users. ▪ Proceed: You need to act fast and conduct on-the-job-training because beneficiaries need commodities urgently.
Questionnaire Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Inform: You should train them first so that they are able to make informed decisions by using iTRACK.

Table 25. Dilemma 8 – What to do when you receive a distress message in an area you are supposed to go

Dilemma	As you are en-route someone presses the iTRACK panic button and sends a message of distress in an area that you are supposed to pass as well. How should you react?
Decision Options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Inform - You need to seek more information to evaluate the reliability and credibility of the data. ▪ Re-route: You should select a safer route. ▪ Proceed: There is no time to verify the information / re-route because the at-risk populations are in dire need.
Questionnaire Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Re-route: You should select a safer route.

Table 26. Dilemma 9 – Determining the level of acceptable risk to send a convoy on mission

Dilemma	How do you determine the level of acceptable risk to send a convoy on a mission?
Decision Options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Evaluate risk: We should seek more information to assess needs versus the risks. ▪ Avoid risk: It is too risky to send a convoy on a mission when there is a chance of a threat occurring. ▪ Accept risk: We should be guided by the at-risk-population needs when making the decision.
Questionnaire Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Avoid risk: It is too risky to send a convoy on a mission when there is a chance of a threat occurring.

Table 27. Dilemma 10 – How to deal with rumors or messages regarding the safety of the mission

Dilemma	Your mission is leading you to an area, for which you hear more and more rumors and messages that it is not safe. What do you do?
Decision Options	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Inform: You need to seek more information, validate it, and check if it is consistent and up to date. ▪ Abandon: You should abandon the mission because the region is not safe. ▪ Proceed: You need to proceed because the beneficiaries are at risk and/or the commodities are perishable.
Questionnaire Results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Inform: You need to seek more information, validate it, and check if it is consistent and up to date.